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Self-Assembly of Polypyrrole Micro-foam/Carbon Nanotube Composite Electrode for Flexible Supercapacitors

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Outline

- Introduction
- Motivation & Objectives
- Fabrication Technique
- Results & Discussion
- Conclusions

The Need of Flexible Energy Storage

Introduction: Electrochemical Capacitors

- Electrical Conductivity
- Specific Surface Area
- Specific Capacitance

Gaps & Motivations

- Low energy densities with current textile energy storage devices, specifically ECs
- Excessive bending and stretching leading to pre-mature cell failure
- Lack of facile fabrication routes for microscale surface modification of EC textile electrodes
- Issues with electrode/electrolyte interfaces

Fabrication: Multilayer Self-Assembly

TPU/CNT

Surface Morphology

- **TPU/CNT Surface**
- Increased surface roughness
- Conductive Layer ensures electron transfer

TPU/CNT/PAni Surface

- Flat morphology
- PAni did not form 3D porous structures
- Attributed to lack to incompatibility during polymerization

Multilayered TPU/CNT/PPyMF Structures

TPU/CNT/PPyMF Surface

- Functionally graded morphology
- PPy microspheres formed 3D structures that facilitates electrolytic ion transfer
- Py monomer swelled TPU/CNT system during polymerization, allowing conductive polymer structures to adhere rightly on the flexible substrate

Multilayered TPU/CNT/PPyMF Structures

TPU/CNT/PPyMF Surface

- PPy Microspheres have diameters of about 851nm on average
- Active layer thickness is about 200-300 μ m
- Can be effectively tuned via changing self-assembly parameters

Electrode Flexibility

TPU/CNT/PPyMF

TPU/CNT/PAni

- Both TPU/CNT/PPyMF and TPU/CNT/PAni electrodes experienced desirable flexibility during testing.
- No permanent deformation observed after repeated bending and flexing.

Electrical Conductivity and Surface Energy

Sample Name	C1s (Atomic %)	N1s (Atomic %)	O1s (Atomic %)
<i>Pristine TPU</i>	71.86	1.98	23.37
<i>TPU/CNT</i>	72.73	3.04	19.62
<i>TPU/CNT/PAni</i>	75.55	6.92	13.16
<i>TPU/CNT/PPyNF</i>	70.03	16.32	4.86

- XPS was performed to confirm the material composition and to verify the growth of the conducting polymers on the surface.
- The increase in nitrogen content indicates successful polymerization since PAni and PPyNF contains nitrogen.
- For TPU/CNT/PAni, due to the lack of adherence of PAni on the surface of TPU/CNT, there was only a slight increase in carbon and nitrogen.
- On the other hand, TPU/CNT/PPyNF system showed a drastic increase in nitrogen content.

Electrical Conductivity and Surface Energy

- Both TPU/CNT/PPyMF and TPU/CNT/PAni electrodes experienced an increase in electrical conductivity, however, due to the conductive polymer microsphere network formation, TPU/CNT/PPyMF has an electrical conductivity of 713.4 S/m on average.
- Water droplet test shows that the PPyMF structures are well structured to facilitate electrolytic ion transfer and would allow interactions with the entire internal surfaces.

Electrochemical Comparisons

Both TPU/CNT/PPyMF and TPU/PPyMF electrodes offered an increase in the capacitance, however, it is shown that the addition of CNT layer contributed to more than 100% increase in the areal specific capacitance due to enhanced PPy growth and adhesion.

Electrochemical Analysis of TPU/CNT/PPyMF

- Capacitance reached 712 mF/cm^2 at a scan rate of 5 mV/s
- Flexing showed minimal effect on capacitance
- Cycling degradation comparable to previous work

Electrochemical Analysis of TPU/CNT/PPyMF

- Throughout the cycling test, Nyquist plots for TPU/CNT/PPyNF stayed consistent during the cycling stability test, which is an indication that the interface between each layer was not substantially affected by the charging/discharging cycling.
- However, for the TPU/PPy samples, the charge transfer resistance at the electrode/electrolyte interface increased drastically, which may be attributed to the interfacial debonding between the PPy layer from the TPU surface.

Conclusions

- Methodology demonstrated a facile method to enhance electrode capacitance performance via microstructuring.
- Sandwiched flexible TPU/CNT/PPyMF structure achieved a specific capacitance of 712 mF/cm².
- Conductive CNT middle layer aided the charge transfer during fabrication and therefore improved the overall performance.
- Repeated bending and stretching showed minimal impact on performance.

Thank You for Your Attention!